

moderately resistant to B1 and bacterial blight and resistant to brown planthopper.

Both varieties are nonlodging under recommended N levels. NLR9672-96 has a droopy flag leaf; NLR27999 shows an erect and medium flag leaf. They have good tillering ability, with more panicles/m² and more grains/panicle than NLR9672 and NLR9674. The 1,000-grain weight does not vary (Table 1).

In replicated wet season trials in 1981-84, NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 consistently gave mean grain yields of 5.5 and 5.3 t/ha, compared to 4.4 and 4.1 t/ha for NLR9672 and NLR9674 (Table 2).

Table 2. Performance of NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 at Nellore, India, 1981-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					Increase over check (%)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			Increase over check (%)	Grain yield ^b 1984
	1981	1982	1983	1984	Mean		1983	1984	Mean		
NLR27999	4.3	5.6	—	6.5	5.5	27.3	6.2	5.1	5.7	9.8	5.3
NLR9672-96	—	—	3.8	6.5	5.2	23.1	—	5.6	5.6	7.1	5.4
NLR9672	3.7	4.8	3.4	—	4.0	—	5.5	4.8	5.2	—	4.3
NLR9674	3.8	5.5	2.6	4.0	4.0	—	—	4.6	4.6	—	—
CD	0.23	0.25	0.19	0.35				0.38			
CV (%)	4.0	3.24	15.01	1.24				16.08			

^aMultilocation trials (mean of 5 locations). ^bMinikit farmers' field trials.

In 1983 multilocation trials in 5 locations, NLR27999 yielded 13% more than NLR9672. In 1984 multilocation trials, NLR27999 yielded 6% more and NLR9672-96 17% more than NLR9672.

In farmers' fields minikit trials with NLR9672 as check, average yields of NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 were 23% and 25% higher than that of NLR9672. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Ratooning ability of 20 F₃ rice crosses

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With rice ratooning becoming a popular cropping system in some areas, breeding for ratooning ability is gaining importance. We did a preliminary study of 8 parents and 20 crosses in the 1984 wet season. Hybrids were represented by the F₃ generation.

Planting was for a minimum population of 102 and a maximum of 3,213 hills/entry (see table). Ratoonability was measured on an individual hill basis.

The main crop was harvested leaving a stubble height of not more than 10 cm; the stubbles were allowed to sprout with only residual moisture. Ratoon growth was measured the third week after main crop cutting. Only hills with at least one fresh, normal-appearing tiller were rated as having regrowth ability.

Ratoonability varied from almost none in Mangala (17%) and Karikagga

Ratooning ability of F₃ populations of various crosses. 1984 wet season, Karnataka, India.

Culture ^a	Sprout (%)	Hills (no.)	Parent used for comparison	Value ^b
Jaya/Mahsuri (D)	100	255	Jaya	+ 2.06*
Jaya/Mahsuri (D)			Mahsuri	+ 0.42 ns
Jaya/Sonamahsuri	99	102	Jaya	+ 0.96 ns
Mahsuri	99	306	—	—
Jaya	98	597	—	—
Mahsuri/Doddi (M)	97	816	Mahsuri	— 2.11*
Jaya/Mahsuri (M)	97	1326	Jaya	— 0.67 ns
Jaya/Mahsuri (M)			Mahsuri	— 2.04*
Purple puttu	97	204	—	—
Mahsuri/IR36	95	3315	Mahsuri	— 3.62**
			IR36	+ 11.87**
Mahsuri/Prakash	95	204	Mahsuri	— 3.71**
Jaya/Mahsuri (T)	95	255	Jaya	— 1.68 ns
			Mahsuri	— 3.07**
Jaya/Type 3 (D)	94	255	Jaya	— 2.82**
Jaya/IR36	94	3213	Jaya	— 3.45**
			IR36	+ 11.49**
Pusa 150/IM1 (T)	93	255	IM1	+ 0.97 ns
Intan mutant 3	93	1224	—	—
Intan mutant 1	91	1011	—	—
Intan mutant 2	91	1011	—	—
Pusa 150/IM1 (M)	90	1836	IM1	— 0.88 ns
IET7031/Mangala	89	867	Mangala	+ 22.52**
Jaya/Type 3 (M)	88	609	Jaya	6.09**
Jaya/Type 3 (T)	87	255	Jaya	— 6.32**
Janaki/Mangala	82	153	Mangala	+ 12.90**
Karikagga/Telhamsa	74	255	Karikagga	+ 20.22**
Pusa 150/Telhamsa	73	510	—	—
Mahsuri/Doddi (T)	65	255	Mahsuri	— 20.6**
IR36	65	102	—	—
Pushpa	43	510	—	—
Mangala	17	255	—	—
Karikagga	4	577	—	—

^aD = dwarf, M = medium, T = tall. ^b** = significant at 1% * = significant at 5%, ns = not significant.

(4%) to high in Mahsuri (99%) (see table). IR36 and Pushpa showed moderate ratoonability.

Based on F₃ data, heterozygous genotypes had higher average ratooning ability (90%) than the pureline parents (64%). This suggests

dominant and heterotic expression of the genes governing inheritance of ratooning ability. Mutants of parents with good ratoonability generally maintained this character, but Intan mutants did not. This indicates recessive genes governing this

character. Further study involving hybrids of parents having total absence of ratoonability, such as Karikagga, and profuse and uniform ratoonability, such as Intan, Mingolo, Intan mutants, and Mahsuri, would be worthwhile. □

Relationship of filled grain percentage to yield

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Nonsynchronous flowering results in differential grain filling. Although panicles have good size and number of spikelets, low yields indicate the need for selecting for a higher percentage of fully filled grains. We studied filled grain patterns in panicles of short- (Rasi, Ratna, and IET8890), medium- (IET7573, IET7574, and IET7575), and long-duration (IET5656, Mahsuri, and Pankaj) varieties.

At harvest, the percentage of filled grains at 1.18 specific gravity was measured for each primary branch. Grain grade was high at the top and low at the bottom, irrespective of variety duration (Fig. 1). Yields correlated positively with grain grade of the lowest branch of the panicle (Fig. 2). Based on the percentage of filled grain on the lowest branch of the panicle, yield potential could be identified as poor (less than 10%), average (20-30%), moderate (30-40%), and high (>50%). □

1. Grain grades on primary branches of panicle. Andhra Pradesh, India.

The International Rice Research Newsletter and the IRRI Reporter are mailed free to qualified individuals and institutions engaged in rice production and training. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.